

Risk Management Analysis in the light of Rumsfeld Matrix – A Study on some selected Companies in India

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ABSTRACT

Risk is an inherent part of every activity. Regardless of the activities the organisation actually goes through, managing risk, by eliminating or mitigating its effects, will yield a greater chance of a favourable outcome. Therefore, an important part of risk management is prioritizing how an organization will eliminate or mitigate risk. An organization's vulnerability as can be perceived, stems less from its decision about whether or not to address risk and more from its failure to identify the existence of risk and to understand the nature of the risk. The very nature of risk is the uncertainty of what one knows. Donald Rumsfeld has identified four types of risks that an organisation may face and these are known knowns, known unknowns, unknown knowns and unknown unknowns. It is of no use to mention that unknown risks have a dangerous yet unfathomable impact like a submerged iceberg. So every organisation, whatever may be its type and nature, should understand the nature of the risks it may face and how to face the challenges arising out of such risks. In this article an attempt has been made to highlight the risks mentioned here encountered by some selected companies operating in India and how to manage those risks.

Keywords: Risk, Rumsfeld Matrix, Strategic risk, Financial risk, Community risk

A. Introduction

Our society day by day has become so complex and its people so interdependent that the failure of one individual among thousands can disrupt the delicate balance of organisation to such an extent that millions may suffer. Here the issue is human behaviour. In order to live effectively in our modern world, we need to gain the very best understandings we can achieve concerning the nature of man and of his behaviour. So, from the view of point understanding the nature of human behaviour up to the view point of running any organisation successfully, there is always some element of risk which we cannot avoid.

In common parlance risk is perceived as uncertainty in the likelihood of a favourable outcome. Risk, on the other hand, is considered a calculation of the probability of an unfavourable outcome. Such unfavourable outcome may cause deleterious effect to the organisation. So, every organisation should think that if there is potential for damage arising out of a given risk, the organisation should try to avoid or mitigate the such risk as far as practicable with proper risk management process. Risk arises out of various reasons and if any one scans risk environment through which different organisations actually go through, he or she can

understand the magnitude of such risks. Leading tech companies viz., Meta (Facebook), Amazon, Alphabet (Google), Apple etc. over the past decades, have been facing various types of risks while doing their businesses. Facebook has faced various types of risks such as - regulatory uncertainty, no access in many countries, Zynga opts for rivals, Mobile dominance of Apple, Google etc. Amazon, on the other hand faces risks viz., increasing competition, profit potential uncertainty, revenue growth uncertainty, speculative valuation and share price volatility etc. In case of Google, there are also risks that are related to culture with respect to hiring right people, maintaining proper balance between how much to diversify in product lines and how much to control, competitions created by Facebook, Twitter, Microsoft, etc. So, whatever may be the nature and size of the company risk is unavoidable.

High levels of risk and complexity is not unknown to the champions of the corporate world. For future growth and development of any organisation risk is one of the important parameters what the organisation cannot avoid. There are various types of risks and these are related to finance, technology, human resource, environment, regulatory compliance etc. All these aspects have a direct bearing on profitability, efficiency and sustainability of any type of organizations whether it is related to business or not.

Risk – The Concept

In common phraseology, risk is defined as variability of returns that implies future uncertainty about deviation from expected earnings or expected outcome.

According to Funk and Wagnall's Encyclopedic Dictionary (1966), risk is defined as exposure to the chance of injury or loss; a chance of encountering harm or loss. Risk is an unavoidable part of doing business that has been mentioned earlier. At present in a world where massive amounts of data are being processed at increasingly rapid rates, recognizing and mitigating risks is a challenge for any company. So, addressing risk requires an organised, focused effort across the enterprise that must encompass consideration of all types of risk. In most of the organisations risk is considered from the financial point of view. But besides financial risk which can be seen and measured, there are other risk as well and that is behavioural risk. This risk arises due to poor workforce behaviours and the cultural factors within which they grow and develop themselves. Such risk affects organisational culture which in long run creates impact on the performance of the organisation. Whatever may be the type of organization, it is imperative to mention that theoretically risk is observed from the view point of financial risk as any risk ultimately affects the profitability and thereby financial condition will be affected. So, it may be opined that risk in relation to those consequences of the activities with respect to something that humans value. The focus of those consequences is normally observed from the viewpoint of their negativity and undesirable consequences.

If we interpret the inherent quality of risk, as Terje Aven (2016) observed, the following qualities of risks immerge -

- “(a) the possibility of an unfortunate occurrence,
- (b) the potential for realisation of unwanted, negative consequences of an event,
- (c) exposure to a proposition (e.g. the occurrence of a loss) of which one is uncertain,

- (d) the consequences of the activity and associated uncertainties,
- (e) uncertainty about and severity of the consequences of an activity with respect to something that humans value,
- (f) the occurrences of some specified consequences of the activity and associated uncertainties,
- (g) the deviation from a reference value and associated uncertainties.”

Risk is subdivided mainly into two types - company specific risk and market risk. Company specific risk is known as unsystematic risk and the other name of market risk is systematic risk. Unsystematic risk is company specific that is caused by such events as strikes, problems relating to marketing programmes, winning and losing of major contracts on which financial success depends to a large extent. On the other hand, systematic risk stems from those factors which affect various organisations simultaneously due to several issues viz., inflation, recessions, war, faster development of new products, quicker adoption of new technologies and so on.

Since the time is changing fast and consumer's lives are changing due to deluge of emerging technologies, the landscape of risks is also changing fast.

B. Objective of the Study

It is quite obvious that every company experiences various types of risks in their life time. Some of the risks are financial in nature and some are non-financial. Again some risks are known to the company and the company knows how to combat such risks. But there are some risks which cannot be estimated in advance i.e., unknown risks. In this article an attempt has been made how risk can be measured and monitored using Rumsfeld Matrix with reference to some selected companies operating in India.

C. Literature Review

Studies on risk management is not new in the business world. Since risk arises out of various incidences, naturally different authors have interpreted the concept of risk as per their perceptions.

Tsai et al (2012), are of opinion that the risk is an indispensable property of any decision and it is measured by a mixture of numerous factors. However, it is generally limited to two factors: sternness and frequency of occurrence of a potentially damaging accidents that include some exposure factors.

Marhavilas et al [2012], the risk is considered as the chance that someone or something that is valued will be unfavorably affected by the hazards, and which have got the features of creating potential damage to the organisation.

According to Heldman (2005), most of us considered risk in terms of its negative consequences. Although risks are potential events that cause threats to projects, they are also

potential opportunities embed in risk. It is an obstacle preventing a project, either positively or negatively, to be delivered based on goals being set.

D. Methodology

To understand the type of risks and their analyses, the above study is based on the following methodologies and these are as under:

- i) Secondary source: The information that are required, have been collected from the annual reports of the selected companies. Besides these, information have also been collected from various text books, journal of national and international repute, internet and websites.
- ii) Sample design: For this study the sample size is three of varied in nature. One sample has been drawn from steel manufacturing giant, the other two are from media house and FMCG respectively and they are TATA Steel, Netflix and Big Bazaar.

Rationale behind choosing different types of organisation for risk analysis:

It is known that while selecting the nature of organisation for discussing any issue in connection with any company requires homogeneity. That means no significant conclusion can be derived if various types of companies are selected for the purpose of any analysis that is related to any company. In this article different types of companies viz., steel manufacturing, media house and FMCG have been chosen in order to examine to what extent Rumsfeld Matrix is at all relevant for all types of companies under reference.

E. Rumsfeld Matrix – The Concept

Donald Henry Rumsfeld (2011) was the former United States Secretary of Defence, when George W. Bush was the president of America. At the time of invasion of Iraq he had developed the Knowns and Unknowns framework. After that people started using quadrants of knowledge and those are known known, known unknown, unknown known, and unknown unknown. Rumsfeld's perception about risk was later turned into a poem written by an unknown poet. The lyrics are as under:

*“As we know,
There are known knowns.
There are things we know we know.
We also know
There are known unknowns.
That is to say
We know there are some things
We do not know.
But there are also unknown unknowns,
The ones we don't know
We do not know.
Finally, there are unknown knowns*

The knowns

We do not want to know.”

According to Rumsfeld, ‘we live in the evidence edge’ and we try to justify policy decisions on the basis of ‘known knowns’. Focus was made mainly on the category of knowledge of human being. So, when the question of decision making arises, it is the duty of the management to identify different environments and how the organisations should proceed accordingly. Rumsfeld had a belief that risks based on knowns and unknowns and these parameters result in four fields of risk which have been presented below with the help of a diagram:

a) Known knowns risks

There are some risks that are very common to company and very much known to the management and the management develops countermeasures to defend such risks. Its identification and assessment are based on fact and knowledge. In this connection an example can be cited. It is a very common phenomena that there is very much possibility of losing of customers base to the competitors in this competitive world and all the companies are aware of such risk. Since losing of customer base results into financial loss, it is the duty of any organisation to reasonably quantify such loss and save the company from impending disaster. This type of risk can be managed and controlled by the management. An example can be cited in this connection with respect to consumer electronics industry. On the demand side such industry faces consumers with unpredictable tastes, on the supply side supplier-related delays or disruptions can be seen and in the middle there is a challenges in production process. Since there is a revolution in technology and to cope up with that, this industry requires large investments but there is hardly any guarantee of proportional returns. This is known known risk in nature. So, when know knowns risk situation arises the management can plan for in

advance to combat the risks. One of the glaring example that can be cited with respect to known knowns risk in connection with TATA Steel is as under:

Strategic risk – Adverse macro-economic environment coupled with global steel capacity may create an impact on TATA’s operating markets and net realisations with respect to cash flows.

Operational risk – The company may incur huge costs if adequate health and safety standards are not maintained that will lead to significant amount of liabilities and the reputation of the company. Non-disposal of plant waste due to limited demand and storage space.

Legal and compliance risk – The outcome of commercial transactions will be affected if there is volatility of foreign exchange.

Safety risk - Non-compliance/delay in implementation of the provisions of safety laws and regulations, which may lead to stoppage of operations, damage to assets and loss of reputation.

Mitigation policy of Known knowns risks adopted by TATA Steel

In order to counteract such known knowns risks TATA Steel had taken various strategic decisions and one of the significant step to address such risk is stated below:

- With respect to strategic risk, the management of TATA had taken initiatives for developing value added products, introducing new brands, diversifying and expanding the customer base. Several cost reduction strategies were also undertaken to mitigate challenging economic conditions.
- When operational risk is to be handled TATA Steel had taken a strategic decision what is known as “Committed to Zero” drive across the Tata Steel Group, and to create awareness and reduce safety accidents.
- In dealing with legal and compliance risk relating to volatility of foreign exchange, foreign exchange hedging policies is to be followed to protect trading and manufacturing margins against rapid and significant foreign exchange movements.
- With respect to mitigating safety risk TATA Steel conducts regular audit and review of the safety measures that are undertaken by the company. Periodic safety trainings are also conducted for employees, contractors and other relevant stakeholders.

b) Known unknown risks

The second category risks is known unknown risks. These types of risks that the management know exists but cannot quantify their potential impact. This arises when the management knows that there is risk but the management does not have all the information about the risk. One example can be cited in this regard. A seasonal factory run by a company is aware of the fact that there is always a chance of rain particularly during rainy season and there is a risk that rain may affect its business operations. It is known risks. But if actual rain falls exceed estimated rains, there arises lack of knowledge and it is very difficult to make concrete plan in this regard. Planning for and perception of risks is difficult but not so difficult. The glaring examples of known unknown risks of TATA Steel are as under:

Community risks: Communities proximate to our operations live through significant socio-economic challenges while retaining a strong cultural heritage and an aspiration to overcome these challenges. The absence of an understanding of this duality in our communities and an inability to maintain a harmonious relationship with them would pose risk to our operations.

Information security risks: Breach of information security events lead to business interruption and damage to reputation. This is known but its impact cannot be properly assessed.

Mitigation policy of Known unknowns risks adopted by TATA Steel

- In order to reduce community risk TATA Steel has adopted the strategy of co-creating scalable solutions for the most endemic development challenges of the communities. TATA Steel has undertaken proven programmes on health, education, livelihood generation, public infrastructure and basic amenities and thereby more than a million lives at TATA's operating locations every year can be protected . Not only that this company has a deep engagement with the tribal community and foster a relationship with the communities by celebrating their history, culture and tribal identity.
- As a measure to lessen information security risks TATA Steel has made admirable efforts to increase awareness and invest in IT security and related compliances. This company has also invested in cyber insurance.

c) Unknown known risks

Negligence of the company is one of the major causes of such risk. If the company believes that there will be no adverse event the company would face, it is a negligence on the part of the company. An example can be cited in this connection with respect to Netflix, the US media house. It is of no use to mention that media industry, like many industries, is in the midst of ongoing shift from their traditional media content distribution and ad sales practices. This is being driven by the ever proliferating number of digital platforms available to consumers for watching TV content and some of such platforms are as under:

- yMVPD's: Sling, Hulu Live, YouTube, AT&T, Philo etc.
- SVOD's, Netflix, Amazon Prime, Apple TV+, Disney+, HBO Max etc.
- FASTs (Free Ad Supported Streaming Television): Pluto, Tubi, Xumo, IMDB etc.

The growing number of options is driving further fragmentation of consumers. Dealing with this shifts is forcing networks to continuously seek ways to drive efficiency in their traditional 'linear' business models exploring the best ways to monetise their content via the digital distribution platforms.

Since there are some threats that all the media houses are facing Netflix is not an exception to that. The unknown risks that Netflix is facing at present is stated below.

International risk – Netflix's international operations involve risks that could adversely affect its business. The nature of such risks, as stated in Netflix's Annual Report 2020, include:

- i) the need to adapt Netflix's content and user interfaces for specific cultural and language differences;
- ii) difficulties and costs associated with staffing and managing foreign operations;
- iii) political or social unrest and economic instability; compliance with laws such as the Foreign Corrupt Practices Act, UK Bribery Act and other anti-corruption laws, export controls and economic sanctions, and local laws prohibiting corrupt payments to government officials;
- iv) difficulties in understanding and complying with local laws, regulations and customs in foreign jurisdictions, including local ownership requirements for streaming content providers;
- v) regulatory requirements or government action against our service, whether in response to enforcement of actual or purported legal and regulatory requirements or otherwise, that results in disruption or non-availability of Netflix's service or particular content in the applicable jurisdiction;
- vi) adverse tax consequences such as those related to changes in tax laws or tax rates or their interpretations, and the related application of judgment in determining Netflix's global provision for income taxes, deferred tax assets or liabilities or other tax liabilities given the ultimate tax determination is uncertain;
- vii) fluctuations in currency exchange rates, which Netflix does not use foreign exchange contracts or derivatives to hedge against and which will impact revenues and expenses of our international operations and expose us to foreign currency exchange rate risk; etc.

Competitor's risk – Netflix occupies significant position in the entertainment zoner. Its main focus is on providing original, timely and collaborative content. Though it is known to Netflix that many streaming service companies viz., HBO Max (Warner Bros), Disney+, Amazon Prime Video, and Apple TV+ etc have entered into the market, and favoured by local people as well as government, Netflix ignores this risk. So there is every possibility of customers' risk when the above mentioned OTT houses enter into the entertainment zoner and thereby, there is risk for future growth and development of Netflix.

Negligence and copy right risks: From the Annual Report 2020 of Netflix it has been observed that as a producer and distributor of content, Netflix faces potential liability for negligence, copyright and trademark infringement, or other claims based on the nature and content of materials that Netflix acquires, produces, license and/or distributes. Netflix also may face potential liability for content used in promoting its service, including marketing materials. Besides these members of Netflix cancel their service for many reasons, including a perception that they do not use the service sufficiently, the need to cut household expenses, availability of content is unsatisfactory, competitive services provide a better value or experience and customer service issues are not satisfactorily resolved.

Mitigation policy of Known knowns risks adopted by Netflix –

In order to reduce risk as far as practicable with respect to international risks that Netflix faces, the management of Netflix should think to develop different pricing strategies and systems for

different markets according to the regional average income level. Since language barrier is one of the important constraints for Netflix, and the company has started facing competitions from similar types of organisations, Netflix should take such an initiative so that it could reach to a larger audience of varied languages. The company can build firm relationships with internet service providers of various countries and take their supports to convert this problem into a positive solution.

As already mentioned, that Netflix has been facing challenges from different OTT media and the names of those media platforms have been mentioned earlier. Since no company at present cannot avoid competitions, it has to develop its own lifeline. Netflix in order to counter this problem, is devoting more resources toward the development, production, marketing and distribution of original programming, including TV series, documentaries and feature films. It believes that original programming can help differentiate its service from other offerings, enhance its brand and otherwise attract and retain members. In order to offer more better services Netflix contracts with third parties related to the development, production, marketing and distribution of its original programming.

In order to reduce political risks Netflix can hire professional resources to carefully study the international markets and regulations before entering a specific market. By doing so, the company can ensure they comply with the local laws and regulations, especially pertaining to censorship, thus avoiding getting sanctioned by local governments.

When it is a question of mitigating financial risks, Netflix can do it by hedging currency risks. By doing this, the company can ensure they maintain a fixed currency exchange rate across different markets they are operating in. This will allow better cost forecasting and planning and would minimize risks against a strengthening US dollar value.

To mitigate customer's risk Netflix could have a fee for customers who prematurely end their membership specified to a certain time. This, however, may make customers become much more reluctant when subscribing in the first place. On the other hand, Netflix can choose to take no actions in changing their packages and accept the related risks, which is ultimately retaining the risk.

d) Unknown unknown risks

These types of risks arise when an organisation is not aware of the existence of such risk. These are very vulnerable type in nature. And as a consequence, it may be opined that the measuring and quantifying such risks cannot be apprehended. One important point in this connection is to be mentioned that risk and uncertainty are sometimes used synonymously. But there is a difference, because a risk represents an event or condition for which the probability of occurrence of an event is known, what is popularly known as the 'known unknowns' condition that is susceptible to analysis. On the other hand, uncertainty is an event for which the probability is not known, being the 'unknown unknowns', and not susceptible to analysis.

The unknown unknowns risks which cannot be understood earlier and on which the organisation has got no control, naturally its negative impact can be noticed on the financial as well as other organs of the organisation and in some cases may endanger the very existence of the organisation. So, it is the riskiest category of risk. The events that cause such risk is called

as *black swan events*. During the 2008 financial crisis arising out of the crash of the U.S. housing market is one of the most current and well-known black swan events.

As an example of this type of risk we can cite the example of Big Bazaar (a part of Future Group), a super market chain of 289 outlets spread pan India. During the first 21-day lockdown due to the Covid-19 pandemic, as per Government order, sales of non-essential items were prohibited. The Central Government has allowed the sale of indispensable items only during the 21-day lockdown. In order to obey the orders, the company had to close its several sections and floors, including fashion, apparel, home, and other non-essential sections. From the Annual Report 2020-21 of Future Retail Limited it transpires that the pandemic, coupled with the lockdown impacted the operations of shopping malls and retail stores across all states. The early stage of the lockdown made an impact on the retail trade severely because there were restrictions on movements of employees, customers and goods. From the said report this observation has been found - *'External environment factors like second wave of COVID-19, impending threat of resurgence of the third wave, spread of the delta variant of Covid-19 and economic factors such as interest rates, inflation, liquidity, rationalisation of tax structure, job creation continue to be the biggest threats. Continued slowdown in the economic activity in the country, no respite from the job losses or challenged income-levels & hence consumption can severely impact Indian retail and therefore growth of the Company.* This type of risk is unknown unknowns risks in nature.

Mitigation policy of Known knowns risks adopted by Big Bazar-

To ensure that the customer can spend lesser time in the shopping mall, the authorities of Big Bazaar was working on it and allowed those customers who were in need of few products. Big Bazaar also has launched an in-store quick-service app in Mumbai. As a pilot on the notion that a customer service executive will help customers to place order for the products using the app, and the order will be delivered on time to their doorstep. This will mean lesser time at the store and a boost for social distancing. On that time this pilot project apparently seemed a success but the Big Bazaar is not thinking about launching the app pan India.

In an alternative way, customers can call a pan-India number and have the products delivered at their doorstep. The company saw a spike in calls for launching of this service.

In order to mitigate other various types of unknown unknowns risks Big Bazaar is vehemently trying to reach out to all the sections of the society. As a consequence Big Bazaar is creating a hypermarket and people from all strata of society such as the rich customers, the middle and the lower class customers come to enjoy the whole shopping experience. To reach to all sections of society Big Bazaar has done huge promotion budgets and it spends significant amount for advertisements to make people aware doing bulk shopping. The main object is not to target at promoting each store, rather only creates an image of Big Bazaar as low-cost shopping option. As a step towards creating awareness among the prospective customers, the store has started advertisement through TV, road shows and also started reality show-typed promotional campaign "The Big Bazaar Challenge." One of the significant strategy to get impressive result was introducing the catch line "Sabse Sasta Din" (Cheapest Day) and it brought forth positive result.

F. Conclusion

The study is over. From the study it appears that various types of companies, be it steel manufacturing company to media house to FMCGs, are facing various types of risks and all the risks they are facing can be placed under four matrix that Rumsfeld has mentioned. Though no company in their annual report has subdivided risks under those categories, however, if such risks can be segregated then due importance can be given to mitigate the type of risk. And this can only be possible when identification the nature of such risks is not the cup of tea of senior managers. As Drucker (2004) mentioned that the decision making process should involve all levels within the organisation. In his opinion the idea that only senior executives make decision or that merely senior executives decision count, runs contrary to the successful decision making process. So every company while categorising the type of risks and how to mitigate them, needs to create risk management team comprising of various stakeholders instead of engaging only managerial personalities and thereby, effective risk management process can be established to exploit the advantage of opportunities on the one hand and stakeholders expectation can be satisfied on the other.

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